

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 18.12.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.01.2026
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 13 (127),124-137

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.18445707

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Mapping the Intellectual Structure of Green Organizational Culture Research: A Bibliometric Analysis (2016–2025)

Yeşil Örgüt Kültürü Araştırmalarının Entelektüel Yapısının Haritalandırılması: Bibliyometrik Bir Analiz (2016–2025)

ABSTRACT

Green organizational culture has become increasingly important as organizations seek to integrate environmental concerns into their values, routines, and everyday practices. In this study, the green organizational culture literature published between 2016 and 2025 is examined through a bibliometric perspective based on 745 articles indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection. The analysis explores publication trends, collaboration patterns, and the conceptual structure of the field using performance indicators, keyword relationships, and thematic approaches. The results show a clear increase in scholarly output over time, with China and the United States standing out as the leading contributors and central actors in international research collaborations. Core themes of the literature are strongly centered on organizational culture and sustainability, while topics such as green organizational climate, green human resource management, and leadership have gained increasing attention in recent years. Overall, this study offers a structured overview of how green organizational culture research has evolved and provides insights that may guide future academic work in this area.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Green Organizational Culture, Sustainability, Bibliometric Analysis, Intellectual Structure Mapping.

ÖZET

Yeşil örgüt kültürü, örgütlerin çevresel kaygıları değerlerine, rutinlerine ve günlük uygulamalarına entegre etme çabaları doğrultusunda giderek daha fazla önem kazanmaktadır. Bu çalışmada, 2016–2025 yılları arasında yayınlanan yeşil örgüt kültürü literatürü, Web of Science Core Collection’da indekslenen 745 makale temel alınarak bibliyometrik bir bakış açısıyla incelenmiştir. Analiz kapsamında; performans göstergeleri, anahtar kelime ilişkileri ve tematik yaklaşımlar aracılığıyla yayın eğilimleri, iş birliği örüntüleri ve alanın kavramsal yapısı ele alınmıştır. Bulgular, zaman içinde akademik üretimde belirgin bir artış olduğunu göstermekte; Çin ve Amerika Birleşik Devletleri uluslararası araştırma iş birliklerinde öne çıkan, alanın lider katkı sağlayıcıları ve merkezi aktörleri olarak dikkat çekmektedir. Literatürdeki temel temaların ağırlıklı olarak örgüt kültürü ve sürdürülebilirlik etrafında şekillendiği; yeşil örgütsel iklim, yeşil insan kaynakları yönetimi ve liderlik gibi konuların ise son yıllarda giderek artan bir ilgi gördüğü tespit edilmiştir. Genel olarak bu çalışma, yeşil örgüt kültürü araştırmalarının zaman içindeki gelişimini sistematik bir biçimde ortaya koymakta ve bu alanda yapılacak gelecekteki akademik çalışmalara yön verebilecek önemli içgörüler sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Örgüt kültürü, Yeşil Örgüt Kültürü, Sürdürülebilirlik, Bibliyometrik Analiz, Entelektüel Yapı Haritalandırması.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, sustainability and environmental responsibility have evolved from being merely strategic choices for organizations into fundamental requirements that transform organizational structures and cultures. The creation of a sustainable environment depends not only on technical and structural practices, but also on employees’ environmentally conscious behaviors. The adoption of an ecological approach across the business, industrial, and service sectors necessitates guiding employees accordingly and encouraging environmentally responsible behaviors (Temminck et al, 2015). In this context, organizations play a guiding role by defining environmentally appropriate workplace behaviors, supporting employees’ motivation in this direction, and managing relationships with stakeholders within a framework of environmental responsibility (Saifulina and Carballo-Penela, 2017). One of the key organizational mechanisms supporting this process is green organizational culture, which integrates environmental values into organizational norms (Banerjee, 2001).

Green organizational culture is conceptualized as the set of values, attitudes, and behaviors adopted by organizational members toward the natural environment (Hadjri et al., 2019). Within this framework, a green business orientation should not be regarded merely as a technical application confined to specific organizational functions; rather, it should be understood as a holistic approach that shapes the organization's overall way of doing business. In the process of fostering sustainability-oriented organizational behaviors, the deliberate and coherent design of organizational culture and climate, leadership styles, ethical principles and codes, organizational structures, human resource management practices, and control mechanisms emerges as a fundamental requirement for achieving positive organizational outcomes (Afacan Fındıklı, 2017).

The organization-wide adoption of green practices results in the transformation of organizational culture into a green organizational culture. The literature demonstrates that green organizational culture enhances organizational productivity, contributes to the development of a positive employer brand image, strengthens organizational innovation and creativity, and serves as a source of competitive advantage for organizations.

Within this theoretical framework, green organizational culture has increasingly been examined in relation to various research domains in recent years, including sustainability, environmental performance, green human resource management, and employee behavior. However, a review of the relevant literature indicates that existing studies have developed in a fragmented manner across different disciplines, methodologies, and thematic foci, and that research providing a comprehensive overview of the field's intellectual structure, core research themes, and evolutionary patterns over time remains limited. In this context, systematically mapping current research trends and uncovering the conceptual structure of the green organizational culture literature is of critical importance. Accordingly, this study examines academic publications in the field of green organizational culture using bibliometric analysis

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data Collection

Nowadays, the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases are widely regarded as two of the most authoritative and extensive sources for conducting bibliometric analyses. These databases offer broad interdisciplinary coverage and index studies published in reputable, peer-reviewed journals.

Web of Science (WoS), in particular, has facilitated the systematic monitoring of scientific publications, citation networks, and emerging research trends on a global scale since the early 1990s. Its Core Collection, which constitutes the backbone of the WoS database, encompasses high-impact journals and scholarly sources across multiple disciplines. Consequently, WoS is commonly acknowledged as a benchmark reference database for analyzing the intellectual structure of the literature, assessing research impact, and examining patterns of scientific collaboration.

In this study, scientific studies published in the field of green organizational behavior were examined using bibliometric analysis methods based on the Web of Science (WoS) database. Access to the relevant publications was obtained on January 13, 2026. The research process and methodological flow followed in the study are presented in Figure 1. During the search process, key concepts representing environmental sustainability and green approaches were considered alongside concepts reflecting organizational culture and climate. The search query developed within this scope yielded a total of 1,118 documents in the Web of Science database. When the time frame was limited to 2016–2025, 851 publications were obtained; the document type filter was applied to consider only articles, and bibliometric analysis was performed on 745 publications.

Figure 1 Research Design

2.2 Bibliometric Analysis Framework

Bibliometric analysis is a widely used research method that enables the systematic and detailed examination of large volumes of scientific data (Algorabi et al., 2024). This approach provides a statistical assessment of scientific developments in a specific research field and offers insights into trends within that field. Interest in bibliometric analysis methods has increased significantly in recent years.

Bibliometric analysis, unlike other approaches to literature review, produces more impartial and consistent results by offering an evaluation based on quantitative indicators (Xiao et al., 2025). In this respect, it contributes to understanding the structure of scientific accumulation by comprehensively revealing the historical development and transformation of a specific research field. Studies conducted in this context serve as an important guide for researchers, decision-makers, and academic institutions in terms of evaluating research performance, interpreting the current dynamics of the field, and determining future research priorities.

Bibliometric approaches are generally addressed under two main headings: performance analysis and scientific mapping. Performance analysis focuses on evaluating the level of scientific contribution of researchers and institutions through publication productivity and citation indicators; this allows academic outputs to be measured quantitatively. Scientific mapping, on the other hand, analyzes interactions between research topics, authors, and institutions using methods such as co-citation, co-keywords, and bibliographic matching, thereby visualizing the intellectual structure of the relevant research field.

In this bibliometric analysis study, Biblioshiny, VOSviewer, and Microsoft Excel software were used to analyze and visualize the data. The study examined publications, authors, countries, publication titles, and collaborative studies; temporal analyses were performed to reveal the development of the field over time. Publication count, citation count, and h-index metrics were used in the performance evaluation; thematic maps were also created to determine the thematic structure of the field.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Publication Analysis

The Web of Science (WoS) category distributions of the 745 publications examined within the scope of bibliometric analysis are presented in Figure 2. The findings show that the studies are predominantly concentrated in disciplines focused on the environment and management. In this context, the categories of Environmental Studies (212 publications), Environmental Sciences (194 publications), and Management (171 publications) stand out as the areas with the highest number of publications. The 121 publications in the Business category constitute approximately 16% of the total publications. Other categories such as economics, engineering, psychology, and interdisciplinary social sciences are represented to a more limited extent. This distribution reveals that green organizational approaches are primarily addressed within the framework of environmental sciences and management literature.

Figure 2 Top 10 Web of Science Categories of The Analyzed Articles.

An examination of the distribution of publications by year, as presented in Figure 3, reveals that scientific output in the field of green organizational approaches has generally followed an upward trend since 2016. While the number of publications was 23 in 2016, this number rose to 63 in 2020 and reached 91 publications in 2022. Although there was a slight decrease in the number of publications in 2023, with 78 publications, there was a significant increase in 2024 (131 publications) and 2025 (154 publications). These findings reveal that the field has experienced rapid growth in terms of academic interest, especially in recent years.

Figure 3 Annual Distribution of Publications Between 2016 and 2025.

Figure 4 presents the total number of citations (TC) and the number of citations per publication (TP/TC) by year. The findings show that total citation counts were relatively high, particularly during the 2017–2021 period. In this context, 2017 stands out as the year with the highest citation count per publication (63.50), revealing that the publications with the highest impact value within the period under review were produced in this year. Although the total number of citations reached its highest level in 2020 with 2,101, 2017 shows

a stronger profile in terms of impact per publication. Despite a noticeable increase in the number of publications in recent years, the relative decrease in citation intensity is noteworthy. The main reason for this is that newly published studies have not yet accumulated sufficient citations because they have not been published long enough. The TC/TP ratio calculated for the 2016–2025 period under review is 18.58, indicating that the field has a stable citation impact in the long term.

Figure 4 Annual Distribution of Total Citations (TC) and Citations Per Publication (TC/TP) Between 2016 and 2025.

Table 1 presents the most cited publications. According to this, the study titled “Effects of Green HRM Practices on Employee Workplace Green Behavior: The Role of Psychological Green Climate and Employee Green Values” published by Dumont, Shen, and Deng (2017) stands out as the most influential article in the field with 896 citations. Overall, the first seven publications on the list have received over 200 citations, indicating that the themes of green human resource management, organizational culture, and sustainability have had a significant impact on the literature. Furthermore, the fact that the most highly cited studies were largely published between 2017 and 2020 reveals that these years represent a critical period in which the conceptual framework of the field took shape.

Table 1 Top 10 Most Influential Articles Based on Total Citation Counts.

Rank	Author	Year	Article Title	Total Citation
1	Dumont, J; Shen, J; Deng, X	2017	Effects of Green HRM Practices on Employee Workplace Green Behavior: The Role of Psychological Green Climate and Employee Green Values	896
2	Isensee, C; Teuteberg, F; Griese, KM; Topi, C	2020	The relationship between organizational culture, sustainability, and digitalization in SMEs: A systematic review	308
3	Zientara, P; Zamojska, A	2018	Green organizational climates and employee pro-environmental behaviour in the hotel industry	291
4	Gürlek, M; Tuna, M	2018	Reinforcing competitive advantage through green organizational culture and green innovation	281
5	Al-Swidi, AK; Gelaidan, HM; Saleh, RM	2021	The joint impact of green human resource management, leadership and organizational culture on employees' green behaviour and organisational environmental performance	266
6	Dubey, R; Gunasekaran, A; Childe, SJ; Papadopoulos, T; Hazen, B; Giannakis, M; Roubaud, D	2017	Examining the effect of external pressures and organizational culture on shaping performance measurement systems (PMS) for sustainability benchmarking: Some empirical findings	259
7	Wang, JR; Xue, YJ; Sun, XL; Yang, J	2020	Green learning orientation, green knowledge acquisition and ambidextrous green innovation	212
8	Martínez-Peláez, R; Ochoa-Brust, A; Rivera, S; Félix, VG; Ostos, R; Brito, H; Félix, RA; Mena, LJ	2023	Role of Digital Transformation for Achieving Sustainability: Mediated Role of Stakeholders, Key Capabilities, and Technology	170
9	Naz, S; Jamshed, S; Nisar, QA; Nasir, N	2023	Green HRM, psychological green climate and pro-environmental behaviors: An efficacious drive towards environmental performance in China	155
10	Chu, ZF; Wang, LL; Lai, FJ	2019	Customer pressure and green innovations at third party logistics providers in China: The moderation effect of organizational culture	146

3.2 Author Analysis

Table 2 ranks the most influential authors based on the number of publications (TP) and total number of citations (TC). According to this, Uddin (7 publications) stands out as the author with the highest publication productivity in this field, followed by Biswas (6 publications). An analysis of the TC/TP ratio, which reflects citation impact, reveals that authors Isensee, Teuteberg, and Griese have high citation values per publication. This indicates that these authors have created a high impact in the literature despite producing a more limited number of publications. When evaluated in terms of the h-index, another performance indicator, it was determined that the h-index of the most influential authors in this field is in the range of 3 and 4. These findings reveal that a core group of authors has emerged in the field of green organizational research, standing out in terms of both productivity and citation impact.

Table 2 Top 10 Most Influential Authors Based on Publication and Citation Metrics.

Rank	Author	TP	TC	TC/TP	H-Index
1	Uddin, Md. Aftab	7	158	22.57	4
2	Biswas, Shetu Ranjan	6	158	26.33	4
3	Isensee, Carmen	4	354	88.50	4
4	Teuteberg, Frank	4	354	88.50	4
5	Griese, Kai-Michael	4	354	88.50	4
6	Salvioni, Daniela	4	200	50.00	3
7	Latan, Hengky	4	149	37.25	3
8	Ho, Jo Ahn	4	135	33.75	4
9	Feng, Taiwen	4	97	24.25	4
10	Dey, Mouri	4	93	23.25	3

3.3 Countries and Institutions Analysis

Figure 5 presents the cumulative number of publications by country over the years. The findings show that China (131 publications) and the United States (85 publications) have made the highest contributions to the field of Green Organizational Behavior. Pakistan and the United Kingdom follow these countries, while Australia, Germany, Spain, and Saudi Arabia have contributed at a more limited level compared to other countries. When examined by period, China produced only 1 publication in 2016, while the United States made an earlier and stronger entry into the field with 9 publications. In contrast, in 2025, China's annual production reached 27 publications, while the United States showed a relatively more limited increase with 14 publications. Furthermore, while the top 10 countries produced a total of 111 publications in 2024, this number rose to 112 in 2025. Throughout the period examined, the fact that the total number of publications by the top 10 countries exceeded 30 indicates that Green Organizational Behavior research has gained popularity in different regions and that the field is growing in strength on a global scale.

Figure 5 Cumulative Number of Publications by Country Between 2016 and 2025.

Figure 6 shows the distribution of institutions by number of publications. The findings indicate that the Egyptian Knowledge Bank and the Ministry of Education Science of Ukraine made the highest institutional contribution with 12 publications. Institutions such as the Chinese Academy of Sciences, Jiangsu University, the University of Chittagong, and the University System of Ohio follow these leading institutions with 8 publications. The publication counts of other institutions are concentrated in the range of 6–7, indicating that research production in the field of green organizational behavior is concentrated in certain centers but is also supported by numerous institutions in different countries.

Figure 6 Top Institutions by Number of Publications.

3.4 Publication Titles Analysis

Table 3 shows the distribution of publications by journal. The findings indicate that the journal *Sustainability* is by far the most productive and influential publication source in the field, with 101 publications, 1,924 citations, and an h-index of 25. In contrast, journals such as the *Journal of Cleaner Production* and *Business Strategy and the Environment* attract attention with their relatively high citation performance despite having much lower publication numbers. Overall, the results reveal that green organizational behavior studies are concentrated primarily in journals focused on sustainability, environmental management, and business strategy.

Table 3 Top Journals Ranked by Publication Output, Total Citations, and H-Index.

Journal	TP	TC	h-index
Sustainability	101	1924	25
Journal of Cleaner Production	23	1788	20
Business Strategy and the Environment	20	574	11
Frontiers in Psychology	13	207	8
Climate Policy	12	297	9
Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	11	316	9
Discover Sustainability	8	12	2
Social Responsibility Journal	8	174	5
Administrative Sciences	7	45	4
Business Strategy and Development	7	57	3

3.5 Collaboration Analysis

The analysis of collaborative studies at the country level was conducted using the VOSviewer software with a co-authorship approach. In the analysis, a minimum publication count of 4 was set for a country to be included in the collaboration network, and the full counting method was used. Figure 7 visualizes the collaboration network between countries. The node sizes on the map represent the number of publications by country, while the connection lines represent the co-publication relationships between countries. The colors show collaboration clusters automatically generated by VOSviewer based on the intensity of co-authorship between countries.

3.6 Timeline Analysis of Research Themes

Figure 9 shows the temporal distribution of author keywords for the last five years (2021–2025). The findings show that the most frequently used keyword in the studies is “organizational culture” (175 times), followed by ‘sustainability’ (57 times), “corporate culture” (42 times), and “culture” (41 times).

An analysis of temporal trends reveals that the themes of “organizational culture” and “sustainability” show a particularly marked increase in 2024 and 2025. In contrast, it is noteworthy that more specific concepts such as “green organizational culture” and “leadership” show a relative decline in 2025 compared to 2024. This indicates a recent conceptual shift in the literature towards the axes of general organizational culture and sustainability.

Figure 9 Temporal Distribution of Authors’ Keywords Over The Last Five Years (2021–2025).

Figure 10 shows the temporal distribution of the most common bigrams (two-word terms) used in publication titles between 2023 and 2025. The findings reveal that the phrase “organizational culture” is by far the most dominant title theme (88 uses in total) and shows a marked increase, particularly in 2024 and 2025.

This is followed by green-focused concepts such as “green climate” (36 times) and “green organizational” (29 times). Furthermore, it is observed that management and human resources-based expressions such as human resource, resource management, and transformational leadership began to be used more frequently in 2025 compared to previous years. Overall, the results show that while the literature at the title level is concentrated on the axis of organizational culture, it is increasingly integrated with green and sustainable management themes.

Figure 10 Temporal Distribution of The Most Frequent Title Bigrams in Publications Between 2023 and 2025.

3.7 Keywords Analysis

The author keyword network presented in Figure 11 clearly reveals the conceptual structure and thematic clusters of the literature. At the center of the network, “organizational culture” is the largest node and is the dominant concept in the field, with strong connections to concepts such as “organizational climate”, “leadership”, and “digital transformation”; this indicates that organizational culture is addressed in conjunction with both managerial and transformational processes. The concepts of “corporate culture”, “corporate governance”, “social responsibility”, and “environmental sustainability”, which stand out in the red cluster at the top, indicate that the studies are concentrated on the axes of corporate governance and sustainability. The green cluster on the left, shaped around terms such as “green organizational culture”, “psychological green climate”, “green HRM”, and “green innovation”, reflects a micro-level research line focusing on environmental behaviors and human resources practices. The purple cluster, located in a more isolated position on the right, is represented by the concepts of “green climate fund” and “climate finance”, showing that financial and policy-based sustainability studies form a separate subfield in the literature. Overall, the colors reveal that the literature exhibits a multi-layered and interdisciplinary structure, extending from the organizational-cultural core to the dimensions of environmental behavior, governance, and finance.

Figure 11 Co-Occurrence Network of Author Keywords.

Figure 12 presents a word cloud based on the Keywords Plus analysis. The findings show that the concepts of “performance” (161 times) and “management” (105 times) stand out by far in the literature, indicating that a performance-oriented perspective dominates the studies. The terms “impact” (95 times) and “innovation” (68 times) indicate that green organizational approaches are strongly associated with organizational outputs and innovation. Furthermore, the high frequency of the concepts “sustainability” (62 times) and “behavior” (57 times) reveals that environmental sustainability and employee behavior are among the fundamental themes of the field. The visibility of terms such as “leadership,” “mediating role,” and “human resource management” suggests that managerial and organizational mechanisms play a mediating role in these relationships.

Figure 12 Keyword Plus Analysis and Word Cloud Based on Web of Science Data

3.8 Thematic Map of Research Themes

Figure 13 presents a thematic map created based on the author's keywords. The thematic map visualizes the intellectual structure of a research field by positioning concepts according to their levels of centrality (relevance/centrality) and density (development/density). The horizontal axis of the map shows the importance of themes within the field, while the vertical axis shows the level of development of the concepts themselves.

In this context, motor themes (high centrality–high density) represent topics that are both well-developed and the driving force of research in the field; fundamental themes (high centrality–low density) represent concepts that are central to the field but relatively less explored; niche themes (low centrality–high density) represent more specific and limited research areas; emerging or declining themes (low centrality–low density) represent newly emerging or declining topics.

The thematic map was created using the Author's Keywords field; the minimum cluster frequency was set to 5 per thousand, the number of tags was 2, and the Walktrap method was chosen as the clustering algorithm. The findings show that the concepts of “organizational culture,” “sustainability,” and “organizational climate” are among the fundamental themes, while concepts such as “green organizational climate” and “corporate social responsibility” form strong research clusters at the center of the field. In contrast, topics such as climate change adaptation, health, and nature-based solutions emerged as more niche themes.

Concepts such as “environmental dynamism”, “innovation performance”, “environmental policy”, and “sustainable agriculture”, located in the Emerging or Declining Themes section of the map, represent themes that are still developing in the field or have the potential to lose relative importance in the literature. Due to their low centrality and density values, these themes lie outside the current research core and may either become emerging topics offering new research opportunities in the future or remain subjects of limited interest in the literature.

Figure 13 Thematic Map of Author Keywords

Figure 14 presents a thematic map created using title bigrams. The analysis reveals how frequently co-occurring concept pairs in publication titles shape the conceptual structure of the field. The map shows that expressions such as “organizational culture”, “organizational climate”, “green human resource management”, and “corporate sustainability” emerge as basic themes. “Sustainable leadership”, “business performance”, and “sustainable business” are among the motor themes, representing the guiding research axes of the field. In contrast, concepts such as “environmental climate”, and “climate change mitigation” are positioned as emerging or weakening themes. These findings demonstrate that title-based analyses offer a complementary perspective in distinguishing mature and emerging research directions in the literature.

Figure 14 Thematic Map of Title Bigrams

4. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Green organizational culture shapes employee behavior and decision-making processes towards sustainability by fostering the adoption of environmental responsibility within the organization. This culture supports environmentally friendly practices while making significant contributions to organizational performance, innovation, and long-term sustainability goals. This study contributes to the literature by examining the green organizational culture literature through a bibliometric analysis, providing a comprehensive overview that reveals the field's development dynamics, prominent themes, and research trends.

The general findings of this study indicate that the green organizational culture literature has grown significantly in recent years and that research has focused particularly on sustainability, organizational culture, and environmental management. A significant portion of the publications originate from China and the US, indicating that these countries are at the center of the field in terms of both publication output and international collaborations. It is also noteworthy that countries such as the United Kingdom and Pakistan have made meaningful contributions to the literature. Thematic and keyword analyses reveal that the concept of organizational culture forms the core of the field, while topics such as green climate, green human resource management, and leadership emerge as supporting and developing research topics. These findings indicate that green organizational culture studies have become a multidisciplinary and increasingly mature field of research.

This study has certain limitations. First, the analyses are limited to the Web of Science database, and studies included in Scopus or other databases have been excluded. Furthermore, since bibliometric analysis depends on the selected time period and keywords, different search strategies may yield varying results. Finally, as the study focuses on quantitative bibliometric indicators, the content depth of the publications examined has not been analyzed in detail.

In future studies, works in the green organizational culture literature can be classified according to their thematic, methodological, or contextual characteristics, enabling more detailed analyses. Classifications based on the conceptual focus of articles, the research methods used, or the sectoral application areas will contribute to a clearer identification of gaps in the literature and dominant research trends.

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